

Farmers' Perception of Risks and Challenges towards Just Energy Transition in Imo State Nigeria

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Abstract: The study evaluated farmers' perceptions on risks and challenges towards just energy transition in Imo state. Structured questionnaires were administered to 450 innovative farmers. Percentages and mean were used to analyse the data. The findings of the study indicate that just energy transition activities most participated by farmers are reskilling and retraining of workers, and environmental restoration. Disease outbreak, air pollution, pest infestation, precipitation pattern, increased temperature, erosion, serious flooding, leaching, weather fluctuation and water pollution were strongly perceived by farmers as just energy transition risks. The respondents acknowledged capacity building, low knowledge of technological investment, energy transition infrastructure, resource revenue and political resistance as the main challenges farmers face towards just energy transition. The respondents mainly adopted resource management, knowledge sharing, and adoption of innovative farm approaches like resistant varieties, climate information and diversification of farm production as adaptive measures towards just energy transition. The provision of just energy transition infrastructure and insurance policy support is critical for farmers to build resilience towards just energy transition.

Keywords: Farmers' Perception, Risks and Challenges, Energy Transition, Disease outbreak, Air pollution

1. Introduction

Just energy transition is one of the outcome of the 27th session Conference of the Parties (COP) of THE United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). It was resolved that in order to achieve food security and protect vulnerable communities, there is need for “Just transition” away from fossil fuels. Energy transition is a concept associated with transitioning from fossil fuels like oil and natural gas to renewable and cleaner energy sources like hydroelectricity, wind, solar and biofuels. This shift to renewable energy arose due to variety of factors namely energy security, economic development and, the need to ameliorate the environmental impact of fossil fuels that induces climate change through release of Green House Gases (Africa App, 2023).

Just energy transition can be achieved through transition from fossil fuels to low carbon economy and by ensuring socio-economic and environmental justice for all (Eisenberg, 2019; Afinotein, 2023). Just energy transition looks into the relationship between those that make energy transition decisions and those affected by the decisions. Developing countries like Nigeria are confronted with the issue of just energy transition on the climate crisis and those working in the agriculture sector are the most hit. Farmers need to develop capacity for socio – ecological resilience; this will enable them to be abreast of various forms of agricultural risks. The just energy transition risks farmers encounter in agriculture include drought, increased temperature, serious flooding, water pollution, air pollution, erosion, leaching, weather fluctuations, salinity, deforestation, disease outbreak, pest infestation and precipitation patterns.

There is need for enactment of effective farming policies that will help farmers to overcome this risk. Achievement of effective

farming policies requires environmental justice which encompasses environmental restoration, access to resources, and equity in distribution of just energy infrastructure and farmers participation in environmental decisions. It also involves serious protection of farm labour inputs through job protection. Others are reskilling and retraining workers in the new industry, enactment of policies for mitigation of climate – related risks and effective monitoring of stakeholders to ensure that transition is carried out in a transparent manner. This is important because the world has passed through many transitions in the past from automation of agricultural industries that leads to loss of agricultural jobs to relocation of food industries. This move caused much hardship on the farmers that depend on the industries for jobs and sales of agricultural products through poor remittance for their livelihood.

Just energy transition in Nigeria is challenged with availability of resource revenue, political resistance by climate change activators, over resource dependence, investment in sustainable technologies, poor infrastructure, capacity building and limited institutional capacity. Others are resource marginalisation, lack of public awareness and competition (Afinotein, 2023). In order to ameliorate the effect of climate change, it is imperative to have clear plans to neutralize the effect of access to various forms of energy for consumptive and productive purposes like electricity, heating, cooking, baking, smoking, processing, production and other uses. This can be affected by inculcating innovative approaches, diversifying farm operations, optimising resource management and building resilience in their agricultural business. To achieve resilience, farmers engage in crop selection/rotation, smart green house, irrigation management, cover cropping, mulching, contour ploughing, conservative tillage, wind breaks, crop diversification,

improved livestock management, energy efficiency, climate information, knowledge sharing, resistant varieties, biological control, water storage facilities, manure management techniques, rotational grazing, optimizing feed formulations, financial resources, insurance policy support and incentives etc. (Machuka, 2023).

The vacuum on farmers' perception on risks and challenges towards just energy transition was the focal point of this study. The study specifically:

- (i) identified participation level of farmers on just energy transition
- (ii) determined farmers perception of just energy transition risks of Imo state
- (iii) ascertained the perception of just energy transition challenges by farmers
- (iv) identified farmers adoption of various adaptive measures against just energy transition

2. Methodology

The study was carried out in Imo state. It falls within the tropical rain forest and is bordered by Anambra state on the North, Rivers state on the South, Abia state on the East, River Niger and Delta state to the west. It lies within latitude 4° 45' N and 7° 15' N and longitude 6° 50' and 7° 25' E and covers an area of about 5100 sq. km. It has three agro-ecological zones namely Owerri, Orlu, and Okigwe. Owerri zone has six LGAs, Orlu zone has twelve LGAs and Okigwe zone has 9 LGAs. The major river in Imo state is the Imo River which drains through Abia River and Akwa Ibom state into the Atlantic Ocean. The population of the state is over 4.8 million people. The state has many natural resources like crude oil, natural gas, lead, zinc, white clay, fine sand, limestone, and wood. The

state has some petroleum industries like Addax Petroleum, Chevron Corporation, Royal Dutch Shell, and Agip. It has many breweries, hydroelectricity, and gas-fired power plants, etc. (SEREDEC, 2017). The main occupation of the people is farming and the state produces crops like oil palm, raffia palm, rice, groundnut, melon, cotton, cocoa, rubber, maize, yam, cassava, cocoyam, etc. They are also involved in the rearing of farm animals like fowl, goats, sheep, pigs, fish, etc. The state was chosen due to its high economic, industrial, and agricultural activities that lead to massive carbon dioxide emissions and climate crisis. A representative sample was chosen using a proportionate sample procedure so that the sampling unit could represent the population spread of the state. Two LGAs were selected from the Owerri zone, three from the Okigwe zone, and four LGAs from the Orlu zone. Lists of registered farmers from the selected LGAs were collected from the Agricultural Development Programme headquarters of the state. This is to ensure that the farmers interviewed were innovative. Five communities were randomly chosen from each LGA selected and twenty respondents were randomly chosen from each community. This gave rise to a sample size of 450. Focus Group Discussion was used to appraise the risks and challenges farmers in Imo state face towards just energy transition. A structured questionnaire was applied as the primary instrument for data collection. Responses on the perception of just energy transition risks and perception of just energy transition challenges were recorded on a five-point Likert-type scale of very strong, strong, average, low, and very low. Using mean score analysis, a discriminatory index of 3 was determined. Based on this discriminatory index, less than 3 indicates minimal risk or challenge, and higher than or equal to 3 indicates strong risk or challenge. Responses on participation level on just energy transition and adoption of various

climate change adaptive measures were analyzed using frequency and percentages.

3. Results and Discussion

Results in Table 1 show the distribution of the farmers according to their level of participation in just energy transition. It projected that farmers interviewed mainly participated in the

reskilling and retraining of farm workers (68.9%) and environmental restoration (63.1%). This revealed that farmers make concerted efforts to key into innovative approaches that reduce climate crisis so that they can have food security and good farm income. This is to enable just energy transition in agriculture to work with the farmers and other stakeholders not against them (Baek et al., 2021) and to check the prevalence of food insecurity (Bhutta, 2018).

Table 1: Participation level of farmers on just energy transition

Just energy transition participation activities	%	Rank
Environmental restoration	63.1	2 nd
Access to resources	40.0	3 rd
Equity in just energy transition infrastructure	30.2	5 th
Reskilling and retraining of workers	68.9	1 st
Enactment of climate mitigation policies	00.0	6 th
Monitoring of just energy transition stakeholders	34.2	4 th

Field survey, 2023 *Multiple responses

Other just energy transition activities participated by farmers include access to resources (40%), monitoring of just energy transition stakeholders (34.2%), and equity in just energy transition infrastructure (30.2%). These low levels of participation are caused by the high cost of productive resources (Gabuz, 2023), poor adoption of renewable energy (Powerforall, 2023), and inequity in just energy transition (Action Aid, 2019). However, the non-participation of the farmers in the enactment of climate mitigation policies could

mean that their opinions are not sought during the enactment of climate mitigation policies. This could be the reason some climate mitigation policies do not address some local climate issues. This hampers just energy transition. Singh et al., (2018) noted that a very good understanding of farmers' participation in climate mitigation policies is imperative for effective and informed enactment of climate change mitigation policies like just energy transition.

The results in Table 2 reveal that disease outbreaks (\bar{X} =4.3), air pollution (\bar{X} =4.1), pest infestation (\bar{X} =4.0), precipitation pattern (\bar{X} =4.0), increased temperature (\bar{X} =3.8), erosion (\bar{X} =3.7), serious flooding (\bar{X} =3.6), leaching (\bar{X} =3.5), weather fluctuation (\bar{X} =3.4), water pollution (\bar{X} =3.3) and deforestation (\bar{X} =3.0)

were the major risks, perceived by farmers due to energy transition processes. The prevalence of climate change risks is a good motivator for farmers to adopt just energy transition measures so that they can build resilience to climate change. This finding agrees with Uddin et al., (2017) position that farmers suffer many

risks as a result of climate change and these risks are interrelated. Sudden disasters like erosion, floods, leaching, drought, and pest infestation are related to rising sea levels and landslides.

Lower risks perceived by farmers were drought (\bar{X} =2.9) and salinity (\bar{X} =2.8).

This finding is in line with Hamal's (2022) finding that energy transition risk perception varies with vulnerability, adaptive capacity, livelihood, and past encounters with climate change. The grand mean of 3.6 implies that farmers have a strong perception of most of the energy transition risks.

Table 2: Perception of farmers on just energy transition risks

Just energy transition risks	Mean	Rank
Drought	2.9	11 th
Increased temperature	3.8*	4 th
Serious flooding	3.6*	6 th
Water pollution	3.3*	9 th
Air pollution	4.1*	2 nd
Erosion	3.7*	5 th
Leaching	3.5*	7 th
Weather fluctuation	3.4*	8 th
Salinity	2.8	12 th
Deforestation	3.0*	10 th
Pest infestation	4.1*	2 nd
Precipitation pattern	4.0*	3 rd
Disease outbreaks	4.3*	1 st
Grand	3.6*	

Source: Field survey, 2023 * Strong perceived risk

Table 3: Perception of farmers on just energy transition challenges

Just energy transition variables	Mean	Rank
Resource revenue	4.0*	3 rd
Political resistance	3.5*	4 th
Low knowledge of technological investment	4.1*	2 nd
Energy transition Infrastructure	4.1*	2 nd
Capacity building	4.6*	1 st
Institutional capacity	2.7	5 th
Resource marginalisation	4.1*	2 nd
Lack of public awareness	2.7	5 th
Grand mean	3.7*	

Source: Field survey, 2023 * Strong perceived risk

The perception of the respondents on just energy transition challenges is presented in

Table 3. It can be deduced from the table that most of the respondents agreed that poor

capacity building (\bar{X} =4.6), low knowledge of technological investment (\bar{X} =4.1), and Energy transition infrastructure (\bar{X} =4.1) are major challenges farmers perceived towards just energy transition. This could be a result of the marginalization of the resources mapped out for mitigation of just energy transition challenges. This affected agricultural resource revenue (\bar{X} =4.0). The challenge of political resistance (\bar{X} =3.5) by the industrial activators of just energy transition is caused by poor climate mitigation policies. Low institutional capacity (\bar{X} =2.7) and lack of public awareness (\bar{X} =2.7) were lowly perceived by farmers as just energy transition challenges. The reason could be that

extension workers do not have access to most energy transition infrastructure that could be used to enlighten farmers. This is supported by Orduno et al.,(2019) opinion that successful implementation of policies aimed at overcoming just energy transition challenges need the cooperation and participation of both the extension agents and the farmers. The grand mean of 3.7 reveals that farmers are increasingly facing incidences of just energy transition. Ramesh et al., (2022) noted that just energy transition challenges impact on agricultural production inducing poverty situation among farmers.

Table 4: Farmers adoption of adaptive measures towards just energy transition

Just energy transition adaptive measures	%
Adoption of innovative farm approaches	91.1
Diversification of farm production	51.1
Resource management	100.0
Utilization of climate information	62.2
Knowledge sharing	100.0
Insurance policy support	33.3
Energy efficiency	22.2
Resistant varieties	66.7

Source: Field survey, 2023 *Multiple responses

100 % of the farmers indicated that resource management is a vital tool to attain just energy transition (Table 4. This could be because most farmers have low access to resources. This must be well managed to meet up with cost of operation. Knowledge sharing (100%) was acknowledged by all the farmers as an adaptive measure towards just energy transition. The reason could be to help farmers utilize climate information which aids them to forecast just energy transition risks. This is in agreement with Meldrin et al.,(2018)findings that farmers need to have knowledge of climate change to enable them implement just energy transition adaptive measures. Adoption of innovative farm approaches (91.1%) was seen by most of the

farmers as an effective adaptive measure towards just energy transition. The reason could be that research institutes monitoring climate changes always come with innovations that can lead to environmental restoration. This concurs with De Matos Carlos et al., (2020) report that farmers adopt innovative practices to achieve just energy transition. Similarly, 66.7% of the farmers indicated that they plant resistant varieties as adaptive measure towards just energy transition, 62.2% said they utilize climate information to ensure just energy transition

and 51.1% resort to diversification of farm production. The implication is that farmers use climate information to identify resistant varieties that enable them to diversify farm production. Less percentage of the farmers took up insurance policy (33.3%) and 22.2% adopted energy efficiency towards just energy transition. The implication is that most of the farmers lack access to resources for the payment of insurance premium and for purchase of just energy transition infrastructure. Adoption of adaptive measures by farmers are constrained by lack of access to information, degree of training participation, financial and agricultural extension services (Ramesh et al., 2022).

4. Conclusion

Just energy transition suffered minimal participation by farmers on enactment of climate mitigation policies, access to energy transition infrastructure, monitoring of just energy transition and access to resources. Just energy transition stakeholders at all levels should ensure equity in distribution of farm resources. The state government, local government and non-governmental organisations should provide farmers with agricultural appliances and renewable energy tool-kit like mini grids, PVS and stem to aid decarbonisation of agricultural activities of production and processing.

Disease outbreaks, pest infestation, air pollution, precipitation pattern, increased temperature, water pollution, serious flooding, leaching, weather fluctuations and deforestation were the perceived risks towards just energy transition. Among the challenges confronting farmers towards just energy transition, the strongly perceived challenges include capacity building, energy transition infrastructure, resource revenue and political resistance by the activators of climate crisis.

Adaptive measures adopted by farmers towards just energy transition manifest in resource management, knowledge sharing, adoption of innovative approaches, utilisation of climate information and diversification of farm production.

There is need to constitute just energy transition committee at the state and local government levels to ensure strict adherence to the just energy transition adaptive measures. This will help to reduce just energy transition risks confronting farmers as well as enable them to overcome just energy transition challenges.

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